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IMPROVEMENT OF THE ADVERTISING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF ENTERPRISES IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION

ВДОСКОНАЛЕННЯ СИСТЕМИ УПРАВЛІННЯ РЕКЛАМНОЮ ДІЯЛЬНІСТЮ ПІДПРИЄМСТВ В УМОВАХ ГЛОБАЛІЗАЦІЇ

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Донець Л.Я., Ніколюк О.В., Значек Р.Р. Вдосконалення системи управління рекламною діяльністю підприємств в умовах глобалізації. Оглядова стаття.

У статті представлено перспективи формування системи управління рекламною діяльністю підприємств в умовах глобалізації. Встановлено, що рекламна діяльність підприємств може проводитись за двома такими напрямками: 1) формування підприємством самостійних організаційних структур, які займаються лише рекламною діяльністю; 2) визначення рекламною діяльністю як ключового напрямку реалізації маркетингової діяльності кожного підприємства. Для сприяння ефективності реалізації цілей, які поставлені перед рекламною діяльністю варто спочатку забезпечити якість відповідних входів, а потім системи управління рекламною діяльністю враховуючи також вплив екзогенних факторів та наявність зворотного зв'язку. Саме таке управління рекламною діяльністю має забезпечити необхідний високоякісний прогноз для параметрів виходу, підвищену якість входів такої системи та врахування екзогенних факторів прямого й непрямого впливу, сприяючи цим самим нормальному протіканню на підприємстві рекламною діяльності.

Ключові слова: управління, рекламна діяльність, система, глобалізація, підприємства

Donets L.Ya., Nikoliuk O.V., Znachek R.R.. Improvement of the advertising management system of enterprises in the conditions of globalization. Review article.

The article presents the prospects of forming a system of management of advertising activities of enterprises in the context of globalization. It is established that advertising activity of enterprises can be carried out in two following directions: 1) formation by the enterprise of independent organizational structures which are engaged only in advertising activity; 2) definition of advertising activity as a key direction of realization of marketing activity of each enterprise. In order to promote the effectiveness of the goals set for advertising, it is necessary to first ensure the quality of the relevant inputs, and then the advertising management system, also taking into account the influence of exogenous factors and the availability of feedback. Such management of advertising activity should provide necessary high-quality forecast for parameters of an exit, the raised quality of inputs of such system and the account of exogenous factors of direct and indirect influence, promoting thereby normal course at the enterprise of advertising activity.

Keywords: management, advertising activity, system, globalization, enterprises

Advertising management is a very important area in modern economics, it solves the global problem of enterprise development and provides consumers with important information. Ukraine, integrating into the world economic space, the globalization of socio-economic processes requires innovative approaches to the implementation of advertising. This component of the national economy is developing rapidly both globally and in Ukraine, and is therefore considered a key direction for its development. From the point of view of psychology, the initial goal of advertising is first of all the formation and preservation of consumer interest in a particular product, which in the future will lead to its acquisition. Thus, this goal can be achieved in two possible cases: if you increase the interest directly in the product by improving the quality properties, reliability and image, and in the case when you pay much attention to the organization of advertising, thus making it more original, save then, in this case, the consumer will be significantly affected by the type of advertisement, but it is most effective to combine the two cases.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Many scientific works of foreign and domestic researchers, namely: J. Burnett, F. Jeffkins, V. Musician, F. Pankratov, N. Pushkarev, O. Feofanova, A. Vovchak and others. have recently been devoted to the problems of solving questions about the development of the advertising management system. Methods for evaluating the effectiveness of advertising, which are adapted to domestic conditions, were proposed by the following scientists: E. Romat, T. Primak, L. Popova, T. Lukyanets.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

However, even taking into account the significant scientific developments in the formation and implementation of the management system of advertising, the question of theoretical and methodological justification of the management system of advertising activities of enterprises in the context of globalization.

The purpose of the article is a theoretical and methodological substantiation of the directions of formation of the management system of advertising activity of enterprises in the conditions of globalization.

The main part

Advertising as a systemic demonstration phenomenon for the modern information and communication space is a necessary area of activity of enterprises. After all, advertising enters the life of every consumer, integrating the functions of a factor that not only largely represents the economic sphere for society, but also reflects and shapes consciousness and culture. Advertising is a so-called regulation by the authorities, and internal organizational and managerial processes that arise directly within the relevant advertising companies, institutions, organizations, and the implementation of their defined management functions by a number of institutions. The organizational and institutional basis for the implementation of advertising is advertising management, which includes the entire advertising process - from market research and presentation of advertising needs to the formation of an advertising product, its presentation and research of the effectiveness of advertising activities. Legislative regulation of advertising is an important component of the socio-economic system of society [1]. The activities of advertisers are directly governed by a wide range of regulations, which primarily regulate the methods of such advertising and sale of goods. Thus, at the international level, the organization of advertising activities is carried out by the International Code of Advertising Practice, which was adopted by the International Chamber of Commerce. The key normative document that regulates legislative relations in advertising management is the Law of Ukraine "On Advertising". Such a law regulates the relevant relations that arise in the process of production, distribution of advertising in certain markets of goods and services, taking into account the markets of banking, insurance and other services related to the use of resources of citizens and legal entities [1].

The basis of advertising activities of each enterprise as a comprehensive system is a program for the management of advertising in accordance with which the main blocks of the organization of advertising management: research, planning of advertising activities, tactical decisions, operational control, evaluation of advertising activities. All such advertising management system is focused on achieving certain socio-economic results in accordance with the strategic objectives of enterprises. Advertising activity of enterprises can be carried out in two following directions: 1) formation by the enterprise of independent organizational structures which are engaged only in advertising activity; 2) definition of advertising activity as a key direction of realization of marketing activity of each enterprise. In modern business conditions, when businesses operate in conditions of fierce market competition, such advertising as one of the possible ways to promote domestic goods to their consumers, is important, as evidenced by the annual increase in advertising costs in domestic and foreign companies. Also, each business entity determines the role of advertising in the organization of its activities.

In turn, the most common form of advertising is the organization of a particular advertising service as one of the components of the marketing department. In the current market conditions of transformation of the national economy there is a need to use qualitatively new methodological approaches to the process of managing the activities of economic entities. The effectiveness of their operation in some way depends on the effectiveness of advertising, which is focused on the development of the business entity, as it intensifies its management activities, focused on taking into account the relevant needs of the market. However, advertising is directly related to some of the costs on the part of the advertiser, so the problem of effective advertising is important for most businesses. First of all, this is due to the high cost of advertising activities in a competitive environment and, as a result, the desire of managers to know how justified the costs of conducting a particular advertising strategy of the business. Advertising activities of enterprises can also be evaluated using various methods, tools and principles and indicators [2].

To promote the effectiveness of the goals of advertising, you should first ensure the quality of the relevant inputs, and then the management system of advertising, also taking into account the influence of exogenous factors and the availability of feedback. Such management of advertising activity should provide necessary high-quality forecast for parameters of an exit, the raised quality of inputs of such system and the account of exogenous factors of direct and indirect influence, promoting thereby normal course at the enterprise of advertising activity.

The key among the factors of market changes that require a change in approaches to the management system of advertising activities of participants in foreign economic activity are the dynamic processes of globalization and development of information and communication technologies. Thus, thanks to the Internet and the opening

of appropriate trade borders, certain consumers have the opportunity to find the best way to solve their problems [3-4]. That is, based on the availability of information, the existence of sustainable interactive communications with most operators in the global market, consumers, comparing existing information about the product from different countries, choose the most advantageous option. In turn, Ukraine today is in a long transition period, which provides for further effective commercial activity for foreign economic entities. On the one hand, this is due to the rather low current level of use of the Internet by Ukrainian manufacturers of information and communication technologies, which significantly slows down their availability in both global and national markets. Thus, for a search query for a significant number of products, the first pages of the relevant search engines belong only to intermediaries, not directly to manufacturers.

Today, many representatives of the national market are beginning to quickly understand the prospects for foreign economic activity, which, accordingly, will threaten a significant increase in competition from the domestic market. Also, Ukrainian consumers, compared to international consumers, are still slowly cooperating with international suppliers, due to distrust of decision-making and logistics at a distance. Despite the significant inertia of domestic consumers, the size of their purchases in global online stores is growing every year by almost 30%. According to a significant number of experts, this trend will continue for Ukraine in the coming years. The desire of consumers to find a better offer on Internet technologies does not exclude their desire to cooperate with those market participants whom they know quite well. In recent years, there has been a tendency to redistribute the terms of use of Internet users from search engines to use the relevant social networks and sites, which include in the list of their personal Internet bookmarks. That is, even such a popular search engine as Google in one recent report predicted a certain decline due to the transformation of social networks into appropriate universal portals with strong alternative internal search engines [5].

The rather high probability of forecasts is explained primarily by the desire of consumers to establish relationships with regular suppliers. The experience of cooperation of consumers with specific suppliers significantly allows them to minimize the possibility of purchasing substandard goods. Under such conditions, among the most important factors for the successful management of any activity (also intermediary) of the subject of foreign economic activity, in addition to attracting new customers, is the maintenance and constant maintenance of relations with existing ones. This will primarily ensure its sustainable operation in the near future. The main areas of competition, which involve the attempt of foreign economic entities to achieve advantages either in range, or in quality, price, at a certain level of service support and others, are exhausted. The only direction that should be included in the so-called inexhaustible and eternal resources - is the universal values and the idea of certain decent relations between the relevant social units of society [6-7].

Thus, the formation of strong and friendly relations with consumers and their social environment in some way allows to form the uniqueness of the subject of foreign economic activity compared to competitors. Thus, the purpose of such a very favorable, strong and unique relationship is to directly satisfy both the socio-economic interests of relevant consumers and their psychological interests, as universal values (confidence, understanding, trust, reputation, etc.), providing a significant increase in communication between the relevant market participants. With this in mind, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of the process of forming such complex positive relations, which form a fundamentally new concept of the management system of advertising activities of foreign economic activity. According to this concept, one of the key places belongs to the strategy of appropriate integrated marketing communications due to its ability to provide consumers with the necessary psychological conditions. One of the important components of such a complex of marketing communications is advertising. This is directly explained by the main advantage of advertising compared to other components - the ability to obtain more contacts with consumers at a lower cost of one such contact. In turn, the main purpose and purpose of advertising for foreign economic activity in the context of globalization is not directly informing consumers about the goods and services, but the algorithmic formation of long-term relationships between consumers and the company.

According to the broadest and most generalized view, the advertising management system should be understood as the search for and implementation of an effective way to achieve the objectives of the relevant advertising activities. However, given the dynamic modern market conditions, businesses view the process of managing personal advertising in a diversified manner, while using several approaches to such optimization. In order to disclose this issue in more detail, we will define the specific properties of the main approaches to building a management system for advertising activities of enterprises. Thus, the process approach reveals the system of advertising management as a complex process of combining and implementing such a process of interconnected functions - a set of permanent and interrelated actions - to develop and achieve goals. Today, a significant number of functions of the control system have been identified. However, they can also be grouped into several key categories relevant to the use of a significant number of businesses in advertising: analysis, planning, forecasting, implementation and control in the management decision-making process for advertising campaigns.

Also, a systematic approach to the organization of advertising management presents it as an important element of the system, ie a set of elements that are combined into a single whole in order to achieve the goal. Thus, only such a presented set of elements makes up the system, forming a whole with fundamentally new specific properties. Important components of such a system are people, certain organizations, knowledge, methods and more. Each such element has its own specific properties and special purpose and is a separate part

of such a system. It performs a function within the system and is not shared during the study of the functioning of such a system. Thus, the specific elements in the system of management of advertising activities of enterprises are separated by their geographical characteristics of management processes in different countries. Based on the above, it is the system approach that such processes must be consistent with each other in a comprehensive system that meets the strategic objectives of the enterprise [8].

Thus, one of the important guarantees of ensuring the required level of competitiveness of enterprises in the context of globalization is a long-term concept of business management, which is to form a strategic and friendly relationship with consumers and society as a whole [9]. According to the concept of business management, the role of complex marketing communications is significantly increasing, one of the important elements of which is advertising. Also, the impact of globalization requires within the main activities of the business entity to separate an additional variety for ancillary and important activities - advertising. Among the presented approaches to the organization of management of advertising activity the complex combination of process, system and situational approaches is substantiated and presented, allowing to consider thus specific features of functioning of the enterprises.

Given the pros and cons of advertising, it should be used so as to provide important information to convince the buyer of the need to purchase a particular product, to minimize the impact of negative factors. Improving the management system of advertising is impossible without compliance with specific conditions: 1. Advertising information must be new and unexpected. 2. Advertising should be used quite actively at the stages of product introduction to the market and a significant increase in sales. 3. Advertising should emphasize the specific features of each product that distinguish it from its counterparts. 4. Advertising is most effective with the corresponding growing demand. 5. Systematic advertising: weekly presentation of information is optimal.

Conclusions

Based on the above information, we can conclude that advertising is an important factor in the development of business and its economic activities. In modern conditions, the advertising management system plays an important role, because it affects the level of popularity of the company and its reputation. The scientific novelty of the presented research lies in the identification of the main process of improving the management system of advertising activities, as well as the main components in its organization and improvement. The study draws attention to the fact that it is advertising relationships with consumers that primarily cause the rapid growth of competitiveness and sales of goods and services, which also affects the level of profit. Advertising can have both positive and negative sides for the company. A very positive aspect of the organization of the advertising campaign is, first of all, that it serves as the largest source of information about relevant products and services for different consumers, acts as a means of controlling the level of product quality and helps increase and maintain demand. Also, provided the effectiveness of advertising activities, it contributes to a significant increase in sales and thus allows to significantly increase the corresponding financial revenues.

Abstract

The article presents the prospects of forming a system of management of advertising activities of enterprises in the context of globalization. The scientific novelty of the presented research lies in the identification of the main process of improving the advertising management system, as well as the main components in its organization and improvement. The study draws attention to the fact that it is advertising relationships with consumers that primarily cause the rapid growth of competitiveness and sales of goods and services, which also affects the level of profit. Advertising can have both positive and negative sides for the company. A very positive aspect of the organization of the advertising campaign is, first of all, that it serves as the largest source of information about relevant products and services for different consumers, acts as a means of controlling the level of product quality and helps increase and maintain demand. According to the concept of business management, the role of complex marketing communications is significantly increasing, one of the important elements of which is advertising. Also, the impact of globalization requires within the main activities of the business entity to separate an additional variety for ancillary and important activities - advertising. Among the presented approaches to the organization of management of advertising activity the complex combination of process, system and situational approaches is substantiated and presented, allowing to consider thus specific features of functioning of the enterprises. In order to promote the effectiveness of the goals set for advertising, it is necessary to first ensure the quality of the relevant inputs, and then the advertising management system, also taking into account the influence of exogenous factors and the availability of feedback. Such management of advertising activity should provide necessary high-quality forecast for parameters of an exit, the raised quality of inputs of such system and the account of exogenous factors of direct and indirect influence, promoting thereby normal course at the enterprise of advertising activity. The advertising management system should be understood as the search for and implementation of an effective way to achieve the objectives of the relevant advertising activities. Improving the management system of advertising is impossible without compliance with specific conditions: 1. Advertising information must be new and unexpected. 2. Advertising should be used quite actively at the stages of product introduction to the market and a significant increase in sales. 3. Advertising should emphasize the specific features of each product that distinguish it from its counterparts. 4. Advertising is most

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